

Supplementary Materials

Meta-Analysis of Artificial Light at Night (ALAN) on Lizard Behavior

Author: Wadhavé Ninad Shirish

Indian Institute of Science Education and Research (IISER), Bhopal, India

Email: wadhavé22@iiserb.ac.in

Contents:

1. final_dataset_corrected.csv – Cleaned dataset with effect sizes and moderators.
2. supplementary_meta_analysis_script.R – Fully reproducible R script.

Dataset Description:

Includes StudyID, Study, Species, Invasive status, Field setting, Lux, sample sizes (n_1 , n_2), effect size (y_i), and variance (v_i).

Requirements:

R with packages: metafor, readr, dplyr (auto-installed by script).

How to Run:

Place both files in the same folder and run:

```
source('supplementary_meta_analysis_script.R')
```

Outputs:

Forest plot, subgroup forest plot, funnel plot, leave-one-out plot, influence diagnostics, Baujat plot, Q-Q plot, and moderator bubble plot (all 300 DPI).

Reproducibility:

All results in the manuscript can be reproduced directly from this dataset and script.

Notes:

Variance (v_i) is computed using Hedges' g formula if not provided. Missing values are removed automatically. Models use REML estimation.

Contact:

wadhavé22@iiserb.ac.in